

IMPACT OF MARGINALIZED STATUS ON EMOTIONAL DISTRESS
FOLLOWING THE RETURN TO REGULAR
UNIVERSITY OPERATIONS

by

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Impact of Marginalized Status on Emotional Distress Following the Return to Regular University Operations

Over the first seven months of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, more than 20 million cases of disease were confirmed and over 730,000 deaths occurred worldwide (World Health Organization, 2020). Since this pandemic, many students have been mandated to continue their education online. Researchers found that while some students might have enjoyed this change, this was not the case for many others (Maqableh & Alia, 2021). College students were forced to tackle more educational stressors during this time such as difficulty concentrating and an increased concern for academic success (Son et al., 2020). One study aiming to research the shift to online learning for undergraduate students examined this issue in two phases. The first phase analyzed the immediate shift from in-person to online learning (Maqableh & Alia, 2021). Researchers found that students experienced an increased workload, inadequate teacher support, higher distractions, reduced focus, and limited resources (Maqableh & Alia, 2021). The second phase evaluated students' satisfaction levels with online learning after three academic semesters. There was an increased level of dissatisfaction with online learning since students stated they faced technological, financial, and time management issues (Maqableh & Alia, 2021). These findings correspond with others, suggesting that college students faced academic COVID-19 stressors (Oh et al., 2021).

Researchers have also explored whether undergraduate students are at risk for increased emotional distress levels following pandemic onset. For example, after academic institutions made their COVID-19 closure announcements, depressive symptoms and anger increased for college students, although anxiety symptoms did not change (Schepis et al., 2021). Other literature found an increase in both depression and anxiety symptoms compared to data collected

before and during COVID-19 (Fruehwirth et al., 2021; Huckins et al., 2020). Through an online survey administered to college students during the COVID-19 pandemic, researchers found that 48.14% had levels of depression and 38.48% had levels of anxiety (Wang et al., 2020). Another researcher surveyed undergraduate students in New Jersey, when the U.S. had the highest number of confirmed cases. It was found that nearly half of students had psychological distress; specifically, the prevalence of general clinical anxiety was 22.3%, and the prevalence of clinical depression was 25.4% (Kibbey et al., 2021). Researchers also found that during a 2020 academic term, there was an increase in sedentary time, anxiety, and depression levels compared to the start of COVID-19 (Huckins et al., 2020). This supports other literature using data from a large academic institution in the United States that found college students' depressive and anxiety symptoms rose after four months of the pandemic (Fruehwirth et al., 2021). It was found that 80% of the students stated they faced psychological issues throughout online learning, such as anxiety (Maqableh & Alia, 2021). Researchers also discovered that COVID-19 concern, financial distress, and infection were also significantly associated with college students' depression and anxiety (Oh et al., 2021). Difficulties in concentrating and employment loss are also associated with high levels of depression for college students (Kecojevic et al., 2020). 71.26% of students reported that both levels increased during the pandemic due to academic stress and uncertainty about the future of the pandemic (Wang et al., 2020).

While the transition to online learning was difficult for many students, it is unclear whether the transition back to largely traditional modes of instruction may also affect psychological distress. Moreover, although students might face less emotional distress because of the return to regular university operations, this might not be the case for all communities. As an example, marginalized groups are disproportionately affected by international and national

crises, including adverse health sequelae (Egede & Walker, 2020; Kantamneni, 2020). Since COVID-19 was a national crisis, researchers focused their efforts on considering how COVID-19 affected marginalized communities compared to non-marginalized communities. It was found that factors caused by structural racism, such as access to health care, living conditions, working environments, and more, have led Black, LatinX, and Pacific Islanders to be more affected by COVID-19 (Hooper et al., 2020). Individuals who identify as Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (BIPOC) are at higher risk than Caucasian-identified individuals for experiencing adversity due to COVID-19 events and anxiety (Hofmann, 2021). After conducting a longitudinal study of psychological distress in a nationally representative sample of adults in the U.S. during the pandemic, researchers found that the ethnic group that reported the highest psychological distress was Hispanics (Breslau et al., 2021). Hispanic adults were also found to have the most frequent symptoms of depression during COVID-19 compared to White, Black, and other non-Hispanics (McKnight-Eily et al., 2021). This also corresponds with other research findings using the COVID-19 Southern Cities Study data, surveying metropolitan cities in the U.S. South. Researchers found that Hispanics and Black respondents had the highest prevalence of psychological distress, while Asian respondents had the lowest (Goldmann et al., 2021). Researchers analyzed data drawn from the Household Pulse Survey, the National Health Interview Survey, and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention COVID-19 Case Reports. Results indicated that Blacks also had increased anxiety levels at the start of the pandemic compared to Whites and Hispanics due to the disproportionately high mortality rates associated with COVID-19 and the Black community (Jacobs & Burch, 2021). Researchers found that ethnic groups of Asian and Hispanic descent had the highest levels of COVID stress (Taylor et al., 2020). Researchers also examined data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination

Survey before COVID-19 to data from the COVID-19 and Life Stressors Impact on Mental Health and Well-Being study during the pandemic. It was found that, pre-pandemic, non-Hispanic Asians had fewer depression symptoms than at the start of the pandemic (Ettman et al., 2020).

Overall, research suggests that marginalized communities faced higher amounts of emotional distress during the COVID-19 pandemic; however, it is uncertain whether specifically marginalized college students also faced higher amounts of distress as well. While examining marginalized college students' emotional distress levels during the transition to in-person university operations, research findings vary. One study found that the communities with the highest levels of anxiety and depression were individuals of mixed race and Caucasian individuals (Oh et al., 2021). Another study found that marginalized college students did not have a greater risk of psychological distress than non-marginalized college students (Kibbey et al., 2021). This corresponds with researchers finding an increase in anxiety symptoms for only White college students (Fruehwirth et al., 2021). They also found no significant changes in anxiety symptoms for Black college students who reported the highest prevalence of anxiety symptoms and Hispanic college students who reported the lowest before the pandemic (Fruehwirth et al., 2021). Even though this research did not find greater psychological distress in marginalized college students compared to non-marginalized students, this significantly differs from other literature findings. Researchers examined the prevalence of depression and anxiety symptoms in a New York City under-sourced public university during COVID-19. They found that the ethnicity that had significantly higher depressive and anxiety symptoms was Latinx (Rudenstine et al., 2021). Researchers also found that the races with the highest prevalence of depression and anxiety symptoms were multi-racial individuals, while Asians still had high

depression symptoms (Rudenstine et al., 2021). Hispanic and Black college students were found to have higher depression symptoms, and Black students were the only ethnic group to have their depression symptoms increase from pre-pandemic (Fruehwirth et al., 2021). It was also found that Black and multi-racial students had the highest anxiety scores, which may have been linked to the disproportionate effects on people of color throughout the pandemic (Hoyt et al., 2021).

Marginalized communities were more likely to be affected throughout the pandemic, resulting in researchers starting to direct their attention to marginalized groups of Asian descent. Because the birthplace of COVID-19 was in China, anti-Asian sentiment has been more prevalent and increasing globally. There has been growing xenophobia and anti-Asian American views ever since the pandemic. The Center for Public Integrity organized a poll of 1000 Americans and found that 32% saw others blaming the Asian population for spreading COVID-19 (Jackson et al., 2020). A third of the surveyed students witnessed others scapegoating Asians for the pandemic (Jackson et al., 2020). After examining self-reported racial discrimination in relation to anxiety, depression, sleep difficulties, and social support of young Asian American adults living in the United States, researchers discovered that Asians had experienced higher rates of racial discrimination during the pandemic (Lee & Waters, 2021).

While marginalized group status may be related to more negative outcomes due to the COVID-19 pandemic, college students of Asian descent may be at risk for increased discrimination. Because the Asian community was blamed and scapegoated for the viral disease of COVID-19, this may have also caused an increase in psychological distress for this community since experiences of racial discrimination are also often associated with increased psychological distress (Branscombe et al., 1999; Fischer & Shaw, 1999; Kessler et al., 1999). Experiencing the increased rates of discrimination due to the pandemic, such as hate crimes,

microaggressions, and vicarious discrimination, was all associated with young Asian adults' poor mental health (Lee & Waters, 2021). This also corresponds with other literature findings from The Healthy Minds Network Study, a web-based survey administered to 28 universities examining college students' mental health to explore the associations between COVID-19 dimensions and mental health outcomes. Researchers found that racial/ethnic discrimination was significantly associated with U.S. college students' depression and anxiety (Oh et al., 2021). After the first wave of a four-wave longitudinal study, it was found that Asian participants reported higher levels of experienced discrimination, which was positively associated with depression and anxiety, and negatively associated with academic engagement (Inman et al., 2021). In comparison, White participants reported higher depression and academic engagement levels (Inman et al., 2021). Researchers considered the psychosocial effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on Asian American college students and found that students had significantly increased perceived discrimination and anxiety symptoms during COVID-19 (Haft & Zhou, 2021). After examining the relationship of experiencing discrimination to academic well-being and psychological distress during the pandemic, researchers found that experiencing discrimination may specifically disproportionately worsen Asian college students' psychological distress and academic engagement (Inman et al., 2021). Non-Hispanic Asian college students were also found to have the highest levels of psychological impact during a cross-sectional study, where data was collected from seven U.S. colleges (Browning et al., 2021).

With the pandemic bringing environmental and educational stressors affecting the well-being of college students, academic institutions need to understand who is most at risk for emotional distress (Hoyt et al., 2021). Students of Asian descent may or may not be at an increased risk of emotional distress due to the rise of anti-Asian discrimination and other

potential COVID-related stressors; however, marginalized communities face high levels of depression and anxiety compared to non-marginalized communities. This makes considering the race and ethnicity of an individual a crucial aspect when researchers analyze marginalized undergraduate students' mental health distress. Now that more academic institutions are back to in-person learning, researchers are starting to investigate the emotional distress levels during this return and may need to focus on marginalized communities. There has only been one known study published analyzing the emotional distress levels of college students returning to in-person classes, and this study was conducted in China. This study investigated the presence of anxiety and depression for undergraduate students after the reopening of school using a cross-sectional survey. The study found that 15.5% showed anxiety symptoms, and 32.4% showed depression symptoms (Ren et al., 2021). Students in higher grades or who had a family member/close friend infected with COVID-19 had higher levels of anxiety and depression (Ren et al., 2021).

Given the potential differential impact of students' transition to more traditional learning, this research will examine emotional distress levels during the return to in-person learning while considering the effects of marginalized group status. The following hypotheses will be examined: 1) Marginalized students will have higher levels of emotional distress symptoms compared to non-marginalized students and 2) discrimination may moderate any relationship between marginalized group status and emotional distress symptoms. This moderation effect may be particularly strong for students identifying as Asian.

Method

Participants

Participants were 172 California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) college students. A web-based participant management system administered through CSUF's Department of

Psychology recruited students. Participants completed online questionnaires in exchange for course credit. Questionnaires assessed the following: demographics, anxiety and depression, COVID-19 stressors, and perceived ethnic/racial discrimination. Participants ranged from 18-28 years old ($M = 19.39$, $SD = 1.8$). On average, there were 55.8% ($n = 96$) freshmen, 14% ($n = 24$) sophomores, 11.6% ($n = 20$) juniors, and 18% ($n = 31$) seniors. The sample consisted of 18% ($n = 31$) males, 79.1% ($n = 136$) females, and 2.3% ($n = 4$) non-binary/genderqueer. Participants identified as the following race/ethnicity: White (14.5%; $n = 25$), Latin/a/x (50%; $n = 86$), Asian (19.2%; $n = 33$), Black/African American (3.5%; $n = 6$), Pacific Islander (1.2%; $n = 2$), and two or more races (9.9%; $n = 17$). Of the 172 participants, 43 (25%) were college students in March 2020 and transitioned from in-person to online learning due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The other 129 (75%) participants were high school students transitioning to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Materials

Demographics

In this researcher-developed questionnaire, participants answered questions regarding their age, gender, race/ethnicity, college year, and whether they transitioned to online learning after March 2020.

Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995)

The Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS) is a self-report questionnaire that consists of 42 items. The DASS measures three emotional states: depression, anxiety, and tension/stress. Sample items include “*I felt that I had lost interest in just about everything,*” and “*I was in a state of nervous tension.*” Participants rated each item using a 4-point Likert Scale, ranging from 0 (*Did not apply to me at all*) to 3 (*Applied to me very much, or most of the time*).

Internal consistency reliability for past samples was .91 for the depression scale, .84 for the anxiety scale, and .90 for the tension/stress scale, demonstrating satisfactory internal consistency (Antony et al., 1998; Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995). Another study evaluating a similar sample found good reliability and validity, specifically the alphas calculated were .96, .92, and .94 (Ruzek et al., 2011)

COVID-19 Stressors Scale (Park et al., 2021)

To assess COVID-19 stress exposure during the pandemic using 23 yes/no questions, researchers created the COVID-19 stressor scale. Sample items include “*Have you experienced risk of becoming infected?*,” and “*Have you experienced loss of current job security or income?*” Using a 5-point Likert Scale ($1 = \text{Not at all stressful}$ to $5 = \text{Extremely stressful}$), participants were asked to rate how stressful each experience was. In a previous study (Tambling et al., 2021), this scale demonstrated a high level of internal consistency ($\alpha = .96$). There was also evidence found that this scale has good convergent and discriminant validity after correlating with other similar measures (Tambling et al., 2021). Specifically, there was a significant positive correlation found between The Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale ($r = .54, p < .001$) and the Perceived Stress Scale ($r = .46, p < .001$).

Perceived Ethnic Discrimination Questionnaire-Community Version (Brondolo et al., 2005)

The Perceived Ethnic Discrimination Questionnaire (PEDQ-CV) is a 34 self-report item that measures perceived ethnic discrimination. Participants were asked how often potential discrimination experiences occur because of their ethnicity/race using a 5-point Likert Scale ranging from $1 = \text{Never}$ to $5 = \text{Very Often}$. Sample items include “*Have you been treated unfairly by teachers, principals, or other staff at school?*,” and “*Have policemen or security officers been*

unfair to you?” Researchers have found good reliability and construct validity in this scale, all alphas > .94 (Brondolo et al., 2005).

Procedure

As stated previously, participants were recruited through the CSUF’s Department of Psychology web-based participant management system (SONA). Interested participants signed up through SONA and were automatically sent to the linked questionnaires through Qualtrics. Approval of this study was granted through the CSUF Institutional Review Board.

Analyses

Hypothesis 1: Marginalized students will have higher levels of emotional distress symptoms compared to non-marginalized students. To examine this hypothesis, a one-way multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) with follow-up t-tests was conducted.

Hypothesis 2: Discrimination may moderate any relationship between marginalized group status and emotional distress symptoms. This moderation effect may be particularly strong for students identifying as Asian. In accordance with the suggestions of Baron and Kenny (1986), after each statistically significant difference in emotional distress between marginalized and non-marginalized groups, moderation tests were conducted. If these tests were found to be significant, additional moderation analyses were conducted to examine whether findings differed based on marginalized Asian versus marginalized non-Asian status.

Results

Of the 172 participants, there were 60.5% ($n = 104$) marginalized non-Asian, 23.3% ($n = 40$) marginalized Asian, and 14.5% ($n = 25$) non-marginalized. On average, college students had experiences of COVID-19 stressors but appraised the experience as not at all stressful or a little stressful, experienced perceived ethnic discrimination to never or rarely during the COVID-19

pandemic, and experienced anxiety and depression symptoms to some degree or a considerable part of the time once back to regular university operations, regardless of marginalized status (see Tables 1 and 2).

To determine whether there was a difference between marginalized status groups for emotional distress symptoms, a one-way MANOVA was conducted. There was a non-significant difference for emotional distress symptoms based on marginalized status, $F(2,168) = 1.72$, $p = .146$; Wilk's lambda = .96, partial eta squared = .02. There was also no difference in emotional distress after controlling for COVID-19 stressors, $F(2,168) = 1.36$, $p = .247$; Wilk's lambda = .968, partial eta squared = .02.

Discussion

The goal of the study was to examine the relationship between college student marginalized status and emotional distress following the return to regular university operations after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. I was also interested in whether discrimination moderated any relationship. Multivariate analyses of variance revealed a non-significant difference for emotional distress symptoms based on marginalized status.

Limitations of this study may have contributed to the null findings. One of the limitations included an uneven, and sometimes relatively low, number of participants in each group, making it challenging to detect statistical significance. Also, the study found that college students experienced COVID-19 stressors but appraised the experience as not at all stressful or a little stressful, which is not in line with recent literature (Maqableh & Alia, 2021; Oh et al., 2021; Son et al., 2020). This study may have not detected statistical significance due to the limited amount of COVID-19-related stress that the students faced. Finally, although all measures demonstrated

reliability, this study relied on self-report data. Self-report may be affected by factors unrelated to this study, including memory limitations.

Despite the null findings, future research could continue to examine these potential relationships, while addressing this study's limitations. Such studies could provide information on ways to support college students in the context of chronic stress. Participants' socioeconomic status (SES) may be another important factor to consider. Researching this relationship in more than one young adult population, e.g., the relationship of college status and degree of COVID-19 stressors, might be another avenue researchers may take to understand how young adults cope with chronic stress.

In sum, these findings suggest that marginalized status does not play a significant role in emotional distress and COVID-19 stressors among college students. Other factors, such as college status or SES, should also be analyzed. Again, more research regarding this relationship may assist in developing and implementing effective interventions for young adults facing emotional distress in the context of ongoing stress.

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Table 1*Psychometric Properties for All Measures*

Measures	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Range
Depression	26.79	9.92	0-42
Anxiety	23.56	8.02	0-42
Stressors	1.79	.66	0-5
Ethnic Discrimination	53.49	15.88	34-170

*Note. n = 172.***Table 2***Means, Standard Deviations, and One-Way ANOVA Statistics for Marginalized Status and Study Measures*

Measures	Non-Marginalized		Marginalized Non-Asian		Marginalized Asian		<i>F</i> ratio	<i>df</i>	η^2
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
	Depression	25.24	9.92	25.88	9.58	30.13			
Anxiety	21.72	6.75	23.35	7.70	25.30	9.32	1.65	2,168	.02
Stressors	1.50	.49	1.83	.62	1.89	.78	17.08***	2,168	.17
Ethnic Discrimination	46.52	13.93	55.39	16.59	53	14.50			

*Note. n = 169. ****p* < .001.*